

INFLUENCE OF FLAW SIZE DISTRIBUTION ON THE SINGLE FIBRE FRAGMENTATION (SFF) TEST

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SUMMARY

The single fibre fragmentation (SFF) test is an important technique used to characterise interface and fibre properties in composite materials. In this work the authors have used a Monte Carlo simulation technique in order to investigate the influence of flaw size characteristics and flaw density on the outcomes of the SFF test.

Keywords: Single fibre fragmentation (SFF) test, Flaw size distribution, Weibull statistics, Monte Carlo simulation

INTRODUCTION

The single fibre fragmentation (SFF) test has been the subject of considerable research for the past two decades or more [1-3]. In its simplest form, this test involves a single brittle fibre being placed at the centre of a more ductile matrix and loaded parallel to the main axis of the fibre – the cross-section of the fibre is taken to be insignificant compared to that of the matrix. The fibre is further assumed to possess a distribution of flaw sizes along its length from which a spatial distribution of strength can be derived; in most models the fibre is divided into discrete sections that are each assigned a random strength according to the size-dependent two-parameter Weibull distribution [4].

Upon loading, the fibre initially breaks at its weakest position with the stress being zero at the fibre fracture position and gradually increasing away from the fracture location until the far-field value, σ_∞ , is reached. The increase in local fibre stress, σ_f , at a distance, x , from the fracture position was initially believed to be linear [5]:

$$\sigma_f(x) = \frac{2\tau x}{r} \quad \text{with} \quad \sigma_f \leq \sigma_\infty \quad (1)$$

where τ is the fibre/matrix interface shear stress and r is the fibre radius. In this region close to the fracture position the fibre is considered to be shielded from further breakages as the load is increased. Whilst Equation (1) is a reasonable first approximation of the stress distribution close to a fibre breakage, later investigations

have indicated the distribution of stress to be more complex [6,7] with a commonly used analysis being that of Cox [8]:

$$\sigma_f(x) = \sigma_\infty \left[1 - \frac{\cosh\left(\frac{l/2-x}{\lambda_o}\right)}{\cosh\left(\frac{l}{2\lambda_o}\right)} \right] \quad (2)$$

where l is the length of the fragment and λ_o is the shear lag load transfer length given by:

$$\lambda_o = r \sqrt{\frac{E_f b}{2G_m r}} \quad (3)$$

where E_f is the fibre elastic modulus, b is the effective interfacial thickness [9,10], and G_m is the matrix shear modulus.

In addition to the distribution of stress at the fragment ends, theoretical models have also taken into account factors such as matrix yielding [11] and residual stress [12], with good correlations between theory and experimental data being noted [13-15].

Whilst the number of fracture positions, and hence fibre fragments, initially increases with further increments of load, there will come a point at which the shielding of fibre fragments is such that no further fibre fracture is possible – known as “saturation”. Analysis of the distribution of fibre fragment lengths upon saturation enables the estimation of τ using [5]:

$$\tau = \frac{r\sigma_c}{l_c} \quad (4)$$

where σ_c is the mean fibre strength at the critical fragment length, l_c , with the value of σ_c being related to the Weibull scale parameter of fibre strength at the critical fragment length, σ_c^* , using:

$$\sigma_c = \sigma_c^* \Gamma(1+1/m) \quad (5)$$

where Γ is the Gamma function. In addition, the relationship between σ_c^* and the Weibull scale parameter of strength in the unbroken fibre gauge length, σ_u , can be estimated using the Weibull scaling rule:

$$\sigma_c^* = \sigma_u \left(\frac{l_c}{L} \right)^{-1/m} \quad (6)$$

where L is the unbroken length of the fibre and m is the Weibull modulus. If the mean fragment length, \bar{l} , is considered instead of l_c then Equation (4) can be approximated by:

$$\tau = 0.75 \frac{r\sigma_c}{\bar{l}} \quad (7)$$

Further work by Henstenburg and Phoenix showed that a more accurate expression for Equation (7) should be [2]:

$$\tau = K \frac{r\sigma_c}{\bar{l}} \quad (8)$$

where K is a function of m and may vary between 0.67 and 0.97 [2]. More recently still, the value of K has been refined to result in [16,17]:

$$K = \frac{(\delta_c/\bar{l})^{-(m+1)/m}}{\Gamma(1+1/m)} \quad (9)$$

where δ_c is a characteristic length [7] with the value of K being <0.75 for the case of $m < 20$.

Several attempts have been made to analyse the SFF test using simulations based on the Monte Carlo technique with the local strength along the fibre length often being given by the following [7,17,18]:

$$\Lambda(\sigma) = \frac{\alpha_0 + (\sigma/\sigma_0)^m}{l_0} \quad (10)$$

where $\Lambda(\sigma)$ is the mean number of flaws per unit length with strength $\leq \sigma$, α_0 is the mean number of initial breaks prior to loading (normally taken to be zero), and σ_0 is the strength scale parameter at a length, l_0 .

In the present work the authors have not assumed the validity of Equation (10) but instead have considered what they believe to be a more fundamental approach by supposing that the flaw sizes followed a well-known flaw size probability distribution and used this information to conduct a Monte Carlo simulation of the SFF test – initial results have been presented in this paper.

As mentioned earlier, in most theoretical models the distribution of strength along the fibre length is generally considered to follow Weibull statistics. However, it is also known that the statistical failure of brittle materials is dependent on factors such as the flaw size probability distribution and number of flaws [19]. Therefore, in this work the authors have investigated the influence of flaw size characteristics and flaw density (*i.e.*, flaw number) on a Monte Carlo simulation of the SFF test – for reasons of space the authors have concentrated on a single SFF outcome, namely the number of fragments, N_{frag} . In addition, rather than dividing the fibre into discrete parts, each with a calculated strength, the authors have used the Poisson-Weibull flaw model to generate a distribution of flaw sizes, and hence strength, randomly located along the fibre length.

The main aim of this work is to determine whether flaw size characteristics and flaw density (in particular the shape of the flaw size distribution in the larger flaw size region) play an important part in influencing the outcomes of the SFF test or, conversely, whether the SFF test is essentially insensitive to the properties of the initial flaw size distribution.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

The overall aim of the authors in carrying out this research was to investigate the influence of flaw size probability distributions on the SFF test and to determine whether this approach produced different results compared to that obtained through use of Equation (10). One important analysis that has tried to correlate flaw size distributions with macroscopic mechanical properties has been that of Jayatilaka and Trustrum [19] who used the following equation for the flaw size probability distribution, $f(a)$, based on the work of Poloniecki and Wilshaw [20]:

$$f(a) = \frac{c^{n-1}}{(n-2)!} a^{-n} e^{-c/a} \quad (11)$$

where a is the semi-flaw size, c is a scaling parameter, and n is the rate at which $f(a)$ decreases for large a – the influence of varying c and n on the shape of $f(a)$ has been shown in Figure 1. The strength at any given flaw size, σ_{flaw} , was calculated using the following expression [21]:

$$\sigma_{flaw} = \frac{K_{IC}}{\sqrt{2a\beta}} \quad (12)$$

Figure 1: Influence of varying shape parameters, n and c , on the Poloniecki and Wilshaw flaw size probability function [20]: (a) varying a with constant c ($c = 1 \times 10^{-8}$), and (b) varying c with constant n ($n = 3$)

where K_{IC} is the critical stress intensity factor and β is the flaw angle. The main result of that work was that m and n were found to be related through the expression [19]:

$$m = 2n - 2 \quad (13)$$

In the present work the authors have incorporated Jayatilaka and Trustrum's theory into a Monte Carlo simulation of the SFF test and investigated the influence of changing the total number of flaws, N , actual fibre/matrix interface stress, τ_{actual} , flaw size parameters, c and n , and fibre length, L , on the SFF test results. The initial values of the simulation have been presented in Table 1 with the value of N being varied between 10 and 10^5 for each simulation.

Unlike previous simulations [2], the number, size (and hence strength), and location of the flaws were chosen prior to the start of the stress loading analysis cycle with the actual number of flaws, N_{actual} , being chosen according to a Poisson process based on the expected value, *i.e.*, N , – this procedure was only carried out for $N \leq 50$ as no influence of $N_{actual} \neq N$ was noted above this value. The strength for each flaw was chosen by selecting a random flaw size (from the cumulative flaw size probability distribution) and a random flaw angle (in the range 0 and $\pi/2$) that were put into Equation (12) whilst the location of each flaw was chosen randomly along the fibre

Table 1: Initial conditions for the simulation (chosen as being typical values for the SFF test).

Parameter	Value
Fracture toughness, K_{IC}	1 MPa·m ^{1/2}
Flaw size parameter, c	10 ⁻⁸ m
Flaw size parameter, n	3 (equivalent to $m = 4$)
Interfacial shear stress, τ_{actual}	10 MPa
Fibre length, L	100 mm
Fibre radius, r	5 μ m

length. Random numbers were chosen according to a linear congruential generator with great care being taken to avoid issues such as serial correlation additional.

Stress loading of the fibre was carried out in increments equal to (a nominally chosen) 1% of the minimum flaw strength and saturation was deemed to have been completed when 10³ stress increments had been completed without a flaw failure having taken place. In order to speed computational times whilst still retaining the essence of the physical processes taking place, the distribution of stress along the axial direction of the fibre adjacent to a fracture location was assumed to be that given by Equation (1).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Prior to simulating the SFF test the general validity of the Monte Carlo analysis method under investigation was confirmed. This was achieved through comparing the Weibull curve generated from the individual strengths of a large number of dry model fibres, *i.e.*, equivalent to a uniaxial tensile test on a population of flaw-containing fibres, with that of the theoretical Weibull curve, $F(\sigma)$, as predicted by Jayatilaka and Trustrum [19]:

$$F(\sigma) = 1 - \exp \left[- \frac{N}{n!} \left(\frac{\pi c}{K_{IC}} \right)^{n-1} \sigma^{2n-2} \right] \quad (14)$$

Results from such a comparison have been presented in Figure 2 with an excellent correlation being noted – it was thus concluded that the statistical simulation under investigation was able to provide correct analysis prior to loading fibres within an SFF test situation.

The influence of n on the number of fragments, N_{frag} , has been presented in Figure 3 with it being noted that N_{frag} increased in a power relationship with regards to N , although this relationship was only valid for fibres containing more than approximately 200 flaws, *i.e.*, there appeared to be a threshold value of N above which $N_{frag} \propto N^y$ – also noted was that y decreased as n increased with the rate of change in y also decreasing with increasing n . The increase in N_{frag} with N was attributed to two related

Figure 2: Comparison between simulated data and theoretical expression derived by Jayatilaka and Trustrum [19] for the following conditions: number of fibres = 10^4 , flaws per fibre = 10^4 , $K_{IC} = 1 \text{ MPa}\cdot\text{m}^{1/2}$, $n = 3$, and $c = 10^{-8} \text{ m}$.

reasons: (i) increasing N would provide a larger number of potential unshielded failure points (*i.e.*, subject to the maximum stress), and (ii) increasing N would tend to result in additional larger flaw sizes being incorporated in the fibre, thus reducing the mean fibre strength and hence l_c – resulting in a greater proportion of the fibre being unshielded.

In contrast to this, the influence of n on N_{frag} was mainly attributed to the shift in the peak mode to smaller flaw sizes with increasing n (Figure 1(a)) that was equivalent to reducing the mean flaw size, and thus increasing the mean flaw strength – this would tend to produce higher fibre stresses at saturation and thus larger l_c , therefore producing a smaller overall unshielded region, leading to a smaller number of fracture points.

In order to negate any change in the shape of $f(a)$ from varying n and/or c , the influence of varying K_{IC} was investigated (as this would change the strength of any given flaw without changing the flaw size itself) with the results being shown in Figure 4.

Similar to the trend shown in the previous figure, the data in Figure 4 appeared to show a power law relationship between N and N_{frag} above a threshold N value of, in this case, approximately 300 flaws with this trend being particularly pronounced for the lowest K_{IC} value of $0.1 \text{ MPa}\cdot\text{m}^{1/2}$. The increase in N_{frag} with N for any given K_{IC} was again

Figure 3: Influence of flaw number, N , and flaw size shape factor, n , on the number of fibre fragments, N_{frag} .

Figure 4: Influence of flaw number, N , and fracture toughness, K_{IC} , on the number of fibre fragments, N_{frag} .

attributed to larger values of N being associated with lower overall flaw strengths (and hence lower saturation stresses) leading to a larger unshielded proportion of the fibre and thus an increased chance of fibre failure. This result appears to suggest that the main factor influencing the number of fragments is the final proportion of fibre within the l_c region rather than overall fibre strength (which may or may not be linked).

In order to test this hypothesis further, the influence of τ_{actual} on N_{frag} was investigated with the results being presented in Figure 5. As mentioned previously, the value of N_{frag} generally increased with N as a power law for the same reasons as mentioned before – the threshold value of N in this case was approximately 100 apart from the situation of $\tau_{actual} = 100$ MPa where the threshold value increased to approximately 1,000 flaws. The value of N_{frag} was found to generally increase with τ_{actual} for any given N with an equal spacing of the curves above $N \cong 1,000$, suggesting N_{frag} to be proportional to τ_{actual} . Given that, with all other variables held constant, the proportion of fibre length at saturation within the l_c regions would be proportional to τ_{actual} , this furthermore suggests that the number of fragments is, as expected, proportional to the portion of fibre within the l_c region.

Figure 5: Influence of flaw number, N , and interfacial shear stress, τ_{actual} , on the number of fibre fragments, N_{frag} .

Figure 6: Influence of flaw number, N , and fibre length, L , on the number of fibre fragments, N_{frag} .

The influence of flaw density on N_{frag} was also investigated by varying the fibre length between 1 and 300 mm for constant N and this has been presented in Figure 6. Apart from the case of $L = 1$ mm, increasing N was found to generally increase N_{frag} , as had been the case for the other variables – the less obvious trend for $L = 1$ mm was attributed to the significant proportion of the fibre being within l_c at saturation. For example, for a stress of 1 GPa a shielded region of 0.25 mm will exist either side of a fracture point and thus the scope for additional fractures will be significantly reduced.

Increasing the value of L corresponded to decreasing the flaw density and thus, at first sight, the number of fragments appeared to increase with decreasing flaw density. However, it would be more appropriate to normalise the number of fragments to a constant L and this has been shown in Figure 7 where the data has been normalised to $L = 100$ mm. The trend of N_{frag} and flaw density (inversely proportional to L) has been reversed in Figure 7 compared to Figure 6 with N_{frag} in Figure 7 being shown to increase with decreasing L , *i.e.*, with increasing flaw density. This trend was explained in terms of the higher flaw density producing an overall lower saturation stress and therefore (at constant τ_{actual}) a larger proportion of unshielded fibre.

Figure 7: Influence of flaw number, N , and fibre length, L , on the number of fibre fragments, N_{frag} , normalized to $L = 100$ mm.

CONCLUSIONS

In this work the influence of flaw size probability distribution parameters and number of flaws on the number of fragments resulting from a Monte Carlo simulation of the single fibre fragmentation test was investigated. The main conclusion was that a minimum number of flaws were required in order to provide valid results – the actual number varied between approximately 100 and 1,000 depending on the parameters under consideration. Above this threshold value the number of fragments generally increased as a power law with respect to flaw number.

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